

MATLAB BASED REAL TIME QUALITY IDENTIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM FOR DIFFERENT GRAIN VARIETIES

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ABSTRACT:

In This proposed system we used Image processing and using this technique we can classify the rice grain sample with accuracy. The morphological features such as (area, perimeter, and length) extracted from the image and are given to classifier. This effort has been prepared to classify the appropriate quality of rice grain sample based on its parameters. To implement this system we used simple night vision web-cam with 20 megapixel intensity. The basic objective of this research is to develop MATLAB based real time system for identification and classification of grain varieties, features such as major axis length, area, minor axis length, and perimeter extracted from the grain image. And this extracted feature is given to the image classifier which classifies and identifies the different grain. And display the result.

KEYWORDS: grain, image processing, morphological features, and MATLAB etc.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Grain quality is complex, and is being determined by the combination of sensory, nutritive, hygienic-toxicological, and technological properties and it is become more important than the quantity. Quality inspection by humans is neither objective nor proficient because the results, sometimes, may not be reliable due to human errors or inexperienced technicians. Therefore a quick and more reliable rice quality evaluation using image processing system can be used.

Digital Image Processing for quality analysis of grains which is very fast, accurate, efficient and cost effective convenient, harmless, non-destructive and cost efficient technique in comparison with the traditional methods which can also achieve high degree of quality. Work needs to be done at the food industry to build some method for the proper extraction of image objects from the background and to remove segmentation errors.

The system consists of several steps such as: image acquisition, Image Pre-processing techniques,

image enhancement, segmentation, thresholding, feature extraction, and morphological feature output are given to the image classifier was developed to identify and classify of different grain varieties. A model of quality testing and identification is built which is based on morphological features & shape technology of image processing and MATLAB. The system will take an image of grain and identifies and classifies the grains and extracted the morphological features on taken image are given to the classifier which identifies the purity and classifications of granule with high accuracy. To implement this we used the digital web camera. This is 20 megapixels of resolution and this input image is given to the system. With the help of interface between the Camera and PC is provided through USB Cable. And these techniques have been implemented using MATLAB and image processing.

II. RELATED WORK:

Some recent reviews explained number of applications on recognition of grain and its growing importance in our daily life This work demonstrates the advancement of the grain recognition systems, with the discussion of many stages are essential to build a complete system with less erroneous using different algorithms.

Table 1: Comparison Between Different Existing systems

Paper & Year	Name of Paper	Author	Work Discussed
IJERT [June-2012]	Grading of Rice Grain By Image Processing	Jagdeep Singh Aulakh , Dr.V.K.Banga	Flat Bed Scanning (FBS) Process is used to find the purity and rejecting the broken grain kernel (full, half or broken).
IJSRP [April 2013]	Classification and Grading Rice Using Multi-Class SVM	Harpreet Kaur, Baljit Singh	The used of Support Vector Machine (SVM) in classifying and grading the rice grain.
IJAREEIE [July 2013]	Machine Vision Technology for ORYZA SATIVA L.(RICE)	Chetna V. Maheshwari	Machine Vision Technology is Used. Quality analysis of different varietal rice via image processing algorithm.
IJSCE [January 2013]	Quality Evaluation of Rice Grains Using Morphological Methods	G.Ajay, M.Suneel, K.Kiran Kumar, P.Siva Prasad	Morphological processing based method for classification of broken rice grains. To perform the rice classification whether broken or not by then method.
IJAREEIE [July 2013]	Matching of Different Rice Grains Using Digital Image Processing	R.Kiruthika, S.Muruganand, Azha Periasamy	BLOB Analysis technique is used to find the quality of rice grains. And Also Varieties of rice grains will be taken and calculated the area, length and shape analysis in digital image processing.
IOSR-JCE [July-august 2014]	Classification and Quality Analysis of Food Grains	Megha R. Siddagangappa, Prof. A. H. Kulkarni	Identification of different types of grains and rice quality based on color and geometrical features using Probabilistic neural network (PNN) and image processing concepts.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Figure drawn below shows the basic block diagram for identification and classification of rice grain System.

Figure1: Block diagram of identification and classification of rice grain System

IMAGE ACQUISER: There are a number of input devices for image acquisition. Some of them are (scanner/camera/CCD) in this system image is acquired by using 20 mega pixel web cam using MATLAB inbuilt command.

IMAGE PREPROCESSOR: Image preprocessing is very important step for image enhancement and for getting good results. The RGB images are captured using a 20 mega pixel webcam. The input sequence of RGB images are converted into gray scale Images. Median filter is used to remove the noise and improve the quality of image. This is also help to preserve edges; segmentation is used to separate the grain image from its background. Thresholding is simple, & effective, way of segmentation it is used to convert the segmented image to a binary image.

FEATURE EXTRACTOR: For feature Extraction different features can be extracted using the function regionprops(). Such as area, major axis length, minor axis length, perimeter of varieties of different grain is calculated.

IMAGE CLASSIFIER: Minimize the distance between the image data and the class in multi feature space. This classifies the different grain varieties and impurity.

IV. RESULT:

A. Results For Identification of Different Grain Quality System

For different varieties of grain we take four different type of grain such as basmati rice, wheat, chana dal, and peas(vatana). Each grain type can repeated ten times, to tested the quality of grain so the total number of tested images was 40. Among all of this 40 sample grain images 32 images of grain quality (impurity) was correct identified and 8 images of grain quality (impurity) was wrong identified.

Table 2: Percentage Accuracy of Different Grain Varieties.

Different Grain Varieties	No. of Tested Images	No. of Correct Tested Images	Error	Percentage of Accuracy
Basmati Rice	10	08	02	80%
Wheat	10	07	03	70%
Chana Dal	10	08	02	80%
Peas	10	09	01	90%

Figure 2: Average Rate for Quality of Different Grain Varieties.

Figure 3: Average Rate for Classification of Different Rice Varieties System.

B. RESULTS FOR CLASSIFICATION OF DIFFERENT RICE VARIETIES SYSTEM

For classification of different rice varieties we take three different sample of rice such as basmati rice, sugndhi chinnor rice, and ambe mohar rice each sample is repeated ten times, so the total number of tested rice sample are 30 among which rice sample from correct classified was 26 i.e. (pure rice such as basmati rice, sugndhi chinnor, and ambe mohar rice) No mixed rice and rice sample from wrong classified i.e. (mixed rice) was 04.

Table 3: Percentage Accuracy of Different Rice Samples.

Different Rice Samples	No. of Tested Images	No. of Correct Classified Images	Error	Percentage Of Accuracy
Basmati Rice	10	10	00	100%
Sugndhi Chiinor Rice	10	08	02	80%
Ambe Mohar Rice	10	08	02	80%

V. CONCLUSION:

The proposed system is very simple and easy to implement as there is no complex feature calculation, no significant amount of training or post-processing required. The systems identify the rice grain and impurity. And also classify the three varieties of rice's using MATLAB software and based on appearance features such as the shape and color, with technology of image processing. This system provides us identification and classification of grain varieties with 80-90% accuracy. A very simple method is proposed for identification and classification of grain varieties. Which require limited features and thus overcoming the disadvantages like tediousness and time consumption the developed method is quick and low cost as there are no costly equipment and software. There is need of research in the area feature extraction and illumination so the system becomes more reliable. The system is more accurate than the human visual inspection which leads to better identify and classify the grain.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Bed Prakash, Amit Yerpude "A Survey on Plant Leaf Disease Identification" International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering Volume 5, Issue 3, March 2015
- 2) Anusha Anchan, Shabari Shedthi B "Classification and Identification of rice grains using Neural Network" International Journal of Innovative

- Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 4, Issue 4, April 2016.
- 3) Megha R. Siddagangappa A. H. Kulkarni, *Classification and Quality Analysis of Food Grains*. IOSR-JCE, Volume 16, Issue 4, Ver. III, pp 01-10 July-August 2014.
 - 4) Chetna V. Maheshwari, "Machine Vision Technology for *Oryza Sativa L. (Rice)*". International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering Volume-2, Issue 7, July 2013.
 - 5) Harpreet Kaur, Baljit Singh, ijsrp, classification and grading of rice grains using multi-class SVM. Volume 3, Issue 4 April 2013.
 - 6) Bhavesh B. Prajapati, Sachin Patel., "Algorithmic approach to quality analysis of Indian basmati rice using digital image processing", International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering International Volume 3, Issue 3, March 2013.
 - 7) G.Ajay, M.Suneel, K.Kiran Kumar, P.Siva Prasad., "Quality Evaluation of Rice Grains Using Morphological Methods", International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE) ISSN: 22312307, Volume-2, Issue-6, January 2013.
 - 8) Jagdeep Singh Aulakh, V.K. Banga. "Grading of rice grains by image processing", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) Vol. 1 Issue 4, June - 2012.
 - 9) Harish S Gujjar, Dr. M. Siddappa "A Method for Identification of Basmati Rice grain of India and Its Quality Using Pattern Classification" International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA) ISSN: 2248-9622 Vol. 3, Issue 1, January - February 2013.
 - 10) Pratt, W. K., "Digital Image Processing", Fourth Edition, A John Wiley & Sons Inc. Publication, 2007.
 - 11) Tarun Kumar, Karun Verma "A Theory Based on Conversion of RGB image to Gray image" International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 - 8887) Volume 7- No.2, September 2010.
 - 12) Parveen, N. R.S., Sathik, M.M., and Gray Scale Conversion Of X-Ray Image, ICISA 2010, and Chennai, 2010, India.
 - 13) Neelamegam. P, Abirami. S, Vishnu Priya. K, Rubalya Valantina.S. "Analysis of rice granules using Image Processing and Neural Network" Proceedings of 2013 IEEE Conference on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT 2013)
 - 14) R. Kiruthika, S. Muruganand, Azha Periasamy "Matching Of Different Rice Grain Using Digital Image Processing" International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering Vol. 2, Issue 7, July 2013.
 - 15) Anusha Anchan, Shabari Shedthi B "Classification and Identification of rice grains Using Neural Network" International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 4, Issue 4, April 2016.